

www.arseam.com

EMPLOYEES PERCEPTION TOWARDS 360 DEGREE FEEDBACK PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SYSTEM

Dr. Neeraj Kumari^{1*}

^{1*} (Corresponding author) Associate
Professor (Department of Management),
FET, Manav Rachna International
University, Aravali Hills, Sector-43,
Faridabad – 121001, Haryana.

Dr. Devi Singh²

Student– Commerce
² Professor & Head (Department of
Physics), FET, Manav Rachna International
University, Aravali Hills, Sector-43,
Faridabad – 121001, Haryana, India

ABSTRACT

To meet the current norms and changing requirements of the corporate the organizations have to choose effective policies. 360 Degree Appraisal System has been found to be one such facilitator of change at individual level. The organization has started the technique of 360-degree appraisal, and it is imperative to gain employee acceptance on the technique and be consistent across the employees. So, the main purpose of the study is to know the perception of the employees about the 360-degree appraisal system. Data is collected through random sampling from 40 employees through questionnaire covering 10 aspects of 360 degree appraisal system. The analysis is done with statistical tools using SPSS. It is found that the employees of the organization feel that 360-degree appraisal system is a tool for complete evaluation. The effective implementation of the 360-degree performance appraisal will increase employee's motivation and better performance thus resulting in better productivity.

Key Words: 360-Degree Appraisal System, expected performance, role and targets, self review, self -serving bias, and training & development needs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globalization is being experienced by the majority of the associations in India. The opportunities and challenges of leadership and management are altogether not the same as that of the past and the most recent decade specifically. There have been transformational administration activities everywhere throughout the world. Evaluation and improvement focuses, Human Resource Development (HRD) scorecard, human capital list and 360-degree criticism are a portion of the significant Human Resource (HR) activities. To walk bear to-bear with the quick pace of advancement it is vital to embrace the most recent patterns and procedures. 360 degree feedback is a system or process in which representatives get classified, mysterious criticism from the general population who work around them in the working environment. This incorporates the

representative's administrator, associates, subordinates and self-survey. The criticism frames incorporate inquiries that are measured on a rating scale and it additionally requests that the separate raters give composed remarks to their associates. The individual, who gets the input, fills a self-rating review. It incorporates similar inquiries that others get in their individual structures. The directors in the association utilize this 360-degree criticism procedure to show signs of improvement photo of their qualities and shortcomings. The outcomes are naturally organized in a legitimate organization along these lines it helps in making an advancement design. The reactions that are gotten from individual and other individuals are consolidated in a similar class so as to protect the secrecy and give the representatives a comprehension of his or her qualities and shortcomings. The organization under study has likewise received the 360-degree criticism framework or multi-rater appraisal framework to have a legitimate assessment of the qualities and shortcomings of its workers. Since it is actualized interestingly, comprehension of the same is essential. There are numerous open doors in the Insurance part and it is developing at a quick pace. Here the prizes are execution based, in the event that you accomplish the objectives you get compensate as commission. There is gigantic rivalry however openings are additionally high. Execution is the watchword henceforth the assessment ought to be on the premise of execution. In this way, with such a large number of difficulties it ends up noticeably essential to have a reasonable assessment framework. Considering these elements, the organization under study has chosen to execute 360-degree input framework. As of late the 360-degree evaluation has turned out to be extremely famous. It has been felt for long that one individual's appraisal of another can't be free of inclinations. Moreover, with the attention on clients (both inside and outside) and accentuation on milder measurements of execution (administration, advancement, collaboration, activity, enthusiastic knowledge, business, and so on.) it has turned out to be important to get numerous appraisals for a more target evaluation. The 360-degree evaluation is a multi-rater assessment and feedback system (MAFS). Practically every Fortune 500 organization is utilizing this in some shape or the other. In this framework, the hopeful is surveyed occasionally (once in a year and a few times even half yearly) by various assessors including his manager, prompt subordinates, associates, and inward and outside clients. The evaluation is made on a survey exceptionally intended to gauge conduct considered basic for execution. The evaluation is done secretly and the appraisal is gathered by an outer operator (expert) or extraordinarily assigned inward specialist (for instance the HRD division). The appraisal is united; input profiles are arranged and given to the member after a workshop or specifically by his supervisor or the HRD division in an execution survey dialog session. Because of the multitudinous varieties conceivable in the 360 Degree Feedback and Appraisals, and its intensity as a competency distinguishing proof and improvement device, it is vital to comprehend the procedure and its progression.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Christopher et al (2017) The outcomes demonstrated that occupation related elements (preparing and advancement, advancement and errands in association positively affected the adequacy of

worker execution evaluation framework among the chose organizations of higher learning in Nakuru Province. A viable execution examination framework empowers associations understand their objectives and in addition workers self-improvement.

Liang et al (2017) The 360° competency evaluation (criticism) prepare not just affirmed the competency level of the appraisal members, additionally distinguished administrative qualities and shortcomings of wellbeing administration supervisors at individual, group and authoritative levels. It is proposed that the venture of associations in helping their chiefs to enhance their administrative skill by including the 360° competency appraisal/criticism handle as one of the key strides.

Zand et al (2017) exhibited that there are important contrasts among the methods for 360 degree as self appraisals, bosses' evaluation, partners' appraisal and representatives' evaluation. Then again, there are important contrasts among the evaluations of chiefs, representatives and employment stretch while there is no noteworthy distinction between the appraisal done on the premise of 360 degree criticism show, self-evaluation, the partners and administrators' evaluations and occupation push.

Helmold & Terry (2017) picking the correct Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) depends upon a decent comprehension of what is critical to the association. "What is vital" frequently relies upon the office measuring the execution – e.g. the KPIs helpful to fund will truly vary from the KPIs doled out to deals. The evaluations regularly prompt the recognizable proof of potential enhancements, so execution pointers are routinely connected with "execution change" activities.

Rizvi (2017) A compelling execution criticism model can assume a key part in an association by improving worker engagement, inspiration and occupation fulfillment. Keeping in see the issues that associations confront inferable from poor criticism culture, the investigation proposes and traces another execution input display that includes a positive quality-focused input approach depending on worker affirmation and fortification.

Karkoulia et al (2016) The aftereffects of the Path Analysis (PA) show that the usage of 360-degree criticism in an association offers ascend to authoritative equity, as well as helps in maintaining this equity and making equity an indispensable piece of the hierarchical culture.

Baradaran et al (2016) showed that examination scores of understudies' execution from the view purpose of clinical teachers have been more noteworthy than that of different gatherings aside from understudies' self-evaluation ($P < 0.001$) and least evaluation score identifies with healing facility conveyed moms who assessed execution lower than different gatherings ($P = 0.0001$). It has been presumed that three hundred sixty degree criticism framework for execution evaluation

is a typical practice for execution examination, and the consequences of it can be utilized as a part of training arranging.

Campion et al (2015) A 360 criticism alludes to the act of requesting unknown evaluations and account remarks at work execution and different practices of the central representative from an extensive variety of other people who have worked with the worker. These sources incorporate companions, subordinates, different directors, and frequently clients, and additionally the prompt administrator and self-evaluations.

Shapiro et al (2016) it is suggested that explaining how pioneer flights influence hierarchical connection requires multilevel speculating and develops.

Kumari (2015) there exists a relationship between perceived fairness of performance appraisal and employee performance. In regression analysis, the nature of the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables was analyzed and the result was that there exists a significant impact of perceived fairness of performance appraisal on employee performance.

Hammerly et al (2014) verified that doctor Emotional Intelligence (EI) assumes a key part in administration; cooperation; and clinical, money related, and hierarchical results. This finding has critical ramifications for social insurance administrators looking to improve doctor arrangement and move to a team-based conveyance display.

Khanna & Sharma (2014) Execution evaluation is a vital apparatus in the hands of individual administration since this procedure finishes the fundamental goal of the branch of the improvement of individuals by assessing the value of the person. The execution administration handle gives a vehicle through which representatives and their bosses' team up to upgrade work results and fulfillment. This procedure is best when both the representative and the administrator play a dynamic part and cooperate to fulfill the destinations of association. Examination happens yearly between the chief and the worker. However there are number of patterns that are changing the style and relationship of the examination.

Kumari (2014) The study concluded that there exists a relationship between perceived fairness of performance appraisal and employee performance. The result of the statistical analysis was that there exists a significant impact of perceived fairness of performance appraisal on employee performance. The study concludes that perceived fairness of performance appraisal behavior plays a very vital role in contributing to organizational functioning and performance thereby giving a better clarity to the relation between employee performance and perceived fairness of performance appraisal.

Mishra (2014) The act of get-together execution criticism from various sources i.e 360-degree input has developed from a creative method to an absolute necessity have device in the general execution and human asset administration methodology.

Kumari (2011) concludes that balanced scorecard is a productivity tool with multiple benefits. It is a strategic performance management tool for measuring whether the smaller - scale operational activities of a company are aligned with its larger - scale objectives in terms of vision and strategy. It can be used as a Strategic Management System that will clarify and translate vision and strategy, communicate and link strategic objectives and measures, plan and set targets with aligning strategic initiatives, enhance strategic feedback and learning.

Kumari (2011) The study measured the level of employee satisfaction at Tata Steel. Training was the factor which contributed to employee satisfaction more than other factors. The other dimensions across which the employee satisfaction was measured were Superior-Subordinate relationship, Role, Culture, Career Development, Goals and Motivation.

DeNisi & Kluger (2000) Execution input is an essential piece of numerous authoritative mediations. Supervisors normally accept that giving workers criticism about their execution makes it more probable that execution at work will be progressed. Regardless of the predominance of criticism components in administration mediations, notwithstanding, input is not generally as powerful as is commonly expected.

Winstanley & Stuart-Smith (1996) Recommends that the option approach used for the situation think about association, the English School of Osteopathy, is especially proper for proficient staff in the not-for-profit segment. Endeavors to consolidate moral worries over execution administration and, utilizing a partner approach, includes those influenced in an exchange over the plan of execution measures and techniques for execution change. Locations four fundamental moral standards, in particular: regard for the individual, common regard, procedural decency and straightforwardness of basic leadership.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Objectives

The objective of the study is:

- 1) To know the perception of the employees about the 360-degree appraisal technique adopted recently.
- 2) To suggest the measures for making it more effective and popular among the employees.

3.2 Statistical Tool

- 1) Sample Size: The total sample size is 40 employees.
- 2) Sampling Type: The sampling used for the study was a ‘simple random sampling’ method.
- 3) Sampling Unit: The sampling unit is only the employees of the organization. Sample unit consists of one employee per questionnaire.
 - Questionnaire: The questionnaire consisting of 10 questions was framed in consultation with the HR Manager and sales manager. The questionnaire aimed at knowing the perception and expectations of the employees, undergoing this process. The analysis is done using SPSS 16.0. The questionnaire was based on these aspects: expectations of employees, true self review, development needs, self -serving bias, feedback, biasness, role and targets, training needs assessment, expected performance, and performance and development
- 4) Type of Research: It is an empirical research.

3.3 Data Collection

- Primary Data: The questionnaire was filled by directly meeting the employees of the organizations.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data were collected from newspapers, magazines, journals, online resources, etc.

4. DATA ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATIONS & FINDINGS

Question 1) The appraisal system followed by your company – 360-degree feedback system gives each employee an idea of what is expected of him or her next year.

Figure 1: showing responses to question 1

Interpretations: The data reveals that more than half of the employees strongly agree that the 360-degree feedback system is an indication about the expectation that the company feels about the same from them as an employee. A small number of employees agree to the same.

Surprisingly, only a small proportion of the employees disagree. This data reflects that the system is in accordance with the expectations of the employees.

Question 2) The 360 degree feedback system gives an opportunity for true self-review.

Figure 2: showing responses to question 2

Interpretations: When the employees were asked about the 360 degree feedback process as a reflection of their self as an employee, the data gathered revealed that all the employees felt this to be the truth. Most of the employees agreed on the issue while some were in strong agreement on the same.

Question 3) The process of appraisal helps the employee to analyze and express his or her developmental needs.

Figure 3: showing responses to question 3

Interpretations: Nearly $\frac{3}{4}$ of the sample agreed with the fact that appraisal helps the employee to analyze and express their developmental needs. The 360 Degree Feedback System gives a clear

picture of the developmental needs as it analyses the positive and negative aspects of the employee.

Question 4) Peer Appraisals are considered as better than self-appraisals because in self-appraisal there are chances of self-serving bias.

Figure 4: showing responses to question 4

Interpretations-The study also delved into the view of the employees regarding the inclusion of peer appraisal as a better system of review as more than half of the employees reported it as a better option. One fourth of the employees were however found to be undecided on the issue while only a small proportion of the employees were found to have a different view regarding the same. This indicates the strength of 360-degree feedback system, as it is a tool for complete evaluation.

Question 5) Employees receiving feedback believe it relates to matters beyond their control.

Figure 5: showing responses to question 5

Interpretations: The study probed into the views of the employees about the control they have on their feedback. Surprisingly, it was found that nearly half of the employees were found to agree

that they did not have much control over the feedback they obtained from their seniors. A large proportion of the employees were found to be undecided on the issue. One tenth of the employees strongly agreed to the issue.

Question 6) 360 Degree Feedback process is free from personal biasness.

Figure 6: showing responses to question 6

Interpretations: The study also found out that whether the employees feel that the system is free from personal biasness or not. It was found out that most of the employees agreed on the issue while a few strongly agreed to the issue. A very few number of employees were found to be undecided on the issue. Only one employee was found to differ in view and disagreed.

Question 7) The present feedback system-360 Degree Feedback System is designed to help the employee and the appraiser jointly understand the role and targets.

Figure 7: showing responses to question 7

Interpretations: The study also gathered information about the mutual benefit of the 360-degree feedback process to the appraiser and respective employee. It was found out that most of the employees were found to agree to the issue while about one tenth of the employees were found to strongly agree on the same.

Question 8) The 360 Degree Feedback System helps in assessment of training needs.

Figure 8: showing responses to question 8

Interpretations: The study enquired about the relevance of the feedback system in respect to the training needs assessment. It was found out that more than 85% of the sample found the 360-degree feedback system to be relevant as far as the training needs are concerned. A small proportion of the employees also felt strongly agreeing on the same. Only a few employees were found to be undecided.

Question 9) An employee is told of what he/she is expected to perform not at the time of appraisal but at the beginning of year.

Figure 9: showing responses to question 9

Interpretations- The data gathered is presented in table 4.9. The study also asked the sample whether they are informed about the expectations that the organization has from them in the beginning of the year. It was found out that all the employees reported to have the complete knowledge of the expectations from them in the beginning of the year.

Question 10) Are the feedbacks provided to individuals based on performance and development?

Figure 10: showing responses to question 10

Interpretations- Most of the employees believed that the feedbacks provided to individuals are based on performance and development. Individuals are rated on their performance and the areas in which they have improved. The feedback system followed is 360 degree and it is done once a year. As it is implemented for the first time at the organization under study, so the employees are expecting a lot from it. Employees have many perceptions and expectations about the new system.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are given to the organization:

- 1) The result of the survey conducted can be used **for development of the senior executives** in areas where they are found lacking and another 360 appraisal can be carried out after a predetermined time frame to evaluate the improvement of the executives.
- 2) 360 Degree Feedback System provides a more balanced evaluation that is more acceptable as fair and reliable. Once when the evaluation is over, the areas of improvement can be assessed and thus, **the training needs can be identified**. Then the areas of improvement can be worked out by developing Training programmes in accordance with the needs.

- 3) The individual **employees must be encouraged** to take charge of getting feedback from their constituencies on a regular basis. This will ensure a wide Performance Management System. Thus the employees will not have to wait for performance improvement programs for long.
- 4) The feedback and follow through process can be handled by a **Trained Professional**. As this system is being launched for the first time in the organization under study so they require expertise. For instance, more work is required when the feedback is negative and unexpected. Managers with low self esteem probably, will have difficulty accepting negative feedback, and will tend to deny the data, and use a variety of defense mechanism to protect themselves from negative results. Managers may rationalize the results by believing that their subordinates and peers do not understand the pressures under which management works. Thus, they might shift the workload to their subordinates or evaluate them poorly on their next performance appraisal.
- 5) The 360 Degree Feedback System can be **free from all kind of personal biasness**. The Appraiser can always be fair in giving ratings to the Appraise. Fair ratings will lead to unbiased results and this will help in boosting up the morale of good performers and motivate others to give their best.
- 6) In Insurance Sector there is one important term “TARGETS” and the whole system revolves around this term. The Key Performance Areas can be clearly specified in the beginning of the year so that it helps the employees to move ahead in a specified direction and pace.
- 7) As the 360 Degree feedback process is being launched for the first time in the organization under study so a special session can be organized to introduce this process. The employees can know about the method of using the process and its benefits for them.
- 8) As 360 Degree Feedback System is an effective process, it can be used as an input of assessment which can enrich an organization’s human resources through identification of individual and organizational goals and philosophy.

6. CONCLUSION

360-degree feedback framework is a procedure in which representatives get private, mysterious input from individuals who work around them in association. 360-degree input can likewise be utilized as a helpful improvement device for individuals who are not in an administration part. It concentrates on assessment of the representative considering every one of the angles. While executing the 360-degree input framework, it is imperative to be steady over the representatives (every one of the workers ought to have an equivalent chance to take an interest in the framework) and directed much of the time. Steady frameworks will be seen as more exact and reasonable. A one-time input practice is not suggested they are best when no less than three to

five terms are arranged. Besides assessing execution extra time furnishes workers with benchmarks for improvement. While actualizing the 360-degree input framework it is basic to get representative acknowledgment.

The following guidelines will help the system to be fair and accurate:

- a. Ensure that the 360degree input framework is the way of life of the association and the desires of the workers.
- b. Conduct a data battle that highlights the advantages of the 360-degree input framework.
- c. Ensure that the rating frameworks are applicable, legitimate and dependable.
- d. Emphasize the significance of the raters being acquainted with the worker's execution and give raters the chance of quitting.
- e. Encourage and prepare raters on the best way to give precise appraisals.
- f. Always advance a taking an interest domain where appraiser and appraisee can talk about the outcomes.
- g. Keep a normal keep an eye on execution evaluation framework.
- h. Communicate data around 360-degree input framework to the representative.
- i. Always approach the representatives with deference and affectability.

Always try to make the process of 360-degree feedback into the culture of the organization. It will appear fairer by doing so. We can make the system effective by considering the following suggestions:

- **Increase employee participation** – employees should always be encouraged to be active participants in the evaluation process. A multiple source feedback works best in an environment that is co-operative and highly team oriented by providing individuals an opportunity to express their views about the systems and processes which results in better performance.
- **Training of feedback providers** – it is important to train the feedback providers to be respectful, polite and sensitive by treating employees in a friendly way as that will make them open to accepting the system.
- **Communication:** Communication is important because people tend to be suspicious of things which they do not understand. Thus, it is important to communicate to the employees the way ratings are done along with the purpose and benefits of 360-degree feedback system.

References

- Baradaran, H. R., Kheirkhah, M., & Keykhosravi, F. (2016). Using a 360 degree feedback system for Performance Appraisal of Midwifery Students in Shahid Akbar Abadi Maternity Hospital. *Development Strategies in Medical Education*, 3(1), 73-80.

- Campion, M. C., Campion, E. D., & Campion, M. A. (2015). Improvements in performance management through the use of 360 feedback. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 8(1), 85-93.
- Christopher, K., Gregory, N., Alice, C., & Elizabeth, N. M. (2017). Determinants of Effectiveness of Employee Performance Appraisal System in Institution of Higher Learning: A Survey of Public Universities in Nakuru County.
- DeNisi, A. S., & Kluger, A. N. (2000). Feedback effectiveness: can 360-degree appraisals be improved?. *The Academy of Management Executive*, 14(1), 129-139.
- Hammerly, M. E., Harmon, L., & Schwaitzberg, S. D. (2014). Good to Great: Using 360-Degree Feedback to Improve Physician Emotional Intelligence. *Journal of Healthcare Management*, 59(5), 354-366.
- Helmold, M., & Terry, B. (2017). Supply Performance Management. In *Global Sourcing and Supply Management Excellence in China* (pp. 81-95). Springer Singapore.
- Karkoulian, S., Assaker, G., & Hallak, R. (2016). An empirical study of 360-degree feedback, organizational justice, and firm sustainability. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(5), 1862-1867.
- Khanna, M., & Sharma, R. K. (2014). Employees performance appraisal and its techniques: a review. *Asian Journal of Advanced Basic Sciences*, 2(2), 51-58.
- Kumari, N. (2011). A Live Study of Employee Satisfaction and Growth Analysis: Tata Steel. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(10), 53-62.
- Kumari, N. (2011). Balanced scorecard for superior organizational performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(5), 73-86.
- Kumari, N. (2014). Using Performance Appraisal as an Effective Tool for Motivating the Employees Performance: A Live Study. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 2(2), 37-46.
- Kumari, N. (2015). To Study the Relationship between Performance Appraisal and Employee Performance in Telecom Sector. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 3(1), 1-5.
- Liang, Z., Howard, P. F., & Leggat, S. G. (2017). 360° management competency assessment: is our understanding adequate?. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 55(2), 213-233.
- Mishra, G. (2014). An Exploratory Study of the Process and Problems of 360-Degree Feedback in Select IT Companies. *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 46(2), 116-122.
- Rizvi, M. A. (2017). A feedback model for an effective performance appraisal system. *Journal for Global Business Advancement*, 10(2), 140-157.
- Shapiro, D. L., Hom, P., Shen, W., & Agarwal, R. (2016). How do leader departures affect subordinates' organizational attachment? A 360-degree relational perspective. *Academy of Management Review*, 41(3), 479-502.
- Winstanley, D., & Stuart-Smith, K. (1996). Policing performance: the ethics of performance management. *Personnel Review*, 25(6), 66-84.
- Zand, H. L., Asadeian, S., & Koshki, N. (2017). Assessment of Managers' Performance and Its Relationship with Job Stress through 360 Degree Feedback Method. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(7), 27-32.